

1st Report on Analysis of Gathered Data including proposal for an EU definition of 'startup'

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1. Introduction

ESNA's data platform serves as a central tool for accessing and sharing information critical to the European startup ecosystem. Recognising the transformative power of data, this report delves into the importance of collecting comprehensive data for the ESNA digital platform and presents the status of the ongoing research proposal for a standardised European Union definition of 'startup'. As the digital ecosystem develops, a robust data foundation is essential for informed decision-making, fostering innovation and ensuring the competitiveness of the European startup ecosystem.

The report has two primary objectives: to explain the importance and current analysis of data collection for the ESNA digital platform and to outline the ongoing research for an harmonised EU definition of 'startup'.

Regarding the importance of data gathering for ESNA, the ESNA data platform is vital in delivering precise and pertinent information to stakeholders for informed decision-making. This involves identifying trends, assessing policy impacts, and facilitating strategic planning. A study data infrastructure provides both startups and policymakers with valuable insights into emerging technologies, market demands and investment trends. This, in turn, aids the establishment of policies that promote innovation and economic growth.

Additionally, the competitive arena is undergoing rapid transformations. By utilising data from ESNA stakeholders and member states, the platform ensures that the European startup ecosystem remains nimble and competitive in the global market.

Currently, member states implement diverse criteria for defining startups, causing inconsistencies and challenges in cross-border collaboration and policy harmonisation. This report advocates for a standardised EU definition of 'startup' to harmonise the classification across member states. A standardised EU definition advances collaboration, facilitates the implementation of coherent policies, and streamlines cross-border operations for startups. Consequently, it contributes to a more robust and interconnected European startup ecosystem.

In conclusion, this report highlights the fundamental importance of data for the ESNA digital platform and ongoing activities towards a standardised EU Startup taxonomy. By addressing these vital aspects, Europe can strengthen its position as a worldwide centre for innovation, entrepreneurship and economic growth.

2. Data Gathering for ESNA Digital Platform

To have a compelling data set for the ESNA Data Platform to provide relevant insights and analytics out of the European Startup Ecosystem, there are 3 groups of Data sources being considered:

- **Startup Data related information.** This dataset includes all relevant data of a startup, including but not limited to age, revenue, number of employees, investment and funding, valuation, seed rounds, industry.
- **Macroeconomic data.** This dataset includes relevant information related to macroeconomic trends within Europe and Rest of the World. Values such as GDP, Inflation, Employment rates, R&D expenditures and other similar metrics may become helpful when combined with startup data to identify trends and insights for better policy making.

- **Member states and country level specific data.** This dataset is related to specific indicators part of country specific regulations. These indicators are to be used when necessary to provide more detailed analytics at the country level. The dataset is based on values from laws related to startups, country-level databases, and similar sources.

Another factor to consider when examining relevant data sources is the target audience of the Data Platform. From this perspective, we have 3 groups of audiences:

- The primary target audience for ESNA consists of member organisations, which are national institutions responsible for implementing entrepreneurship, startup, and SME policies in Member States and EEA countries. These organisations will be key beneficiaries of the ESNA digital platform, utilizing it for the adoption and implementation of Startup Nation Standard (SNS) best practices. ESNA's role extends beyond the Data Platform through other Action Areas to support these entities by promoting best practice exchange, capacity building, knowledge sharing, and the gathering, analysis, and dissemination of critical data.
- At a secondary level, the impact of ESNA's activities will reach a broad spectrum of stakeholders within the national startup ecosystems. This encompasses startups themselves, as well as the investment community, which includes corporations, business angels, seed and venture capital funds and firms, and investment firms. Researchers and universities, policy makers at various levels, relevant NGOs, and other entities contributing to or benefiting from the development of national startup ecosystems will also be engaged.
- A third significant target group for the project includes media and civil society. Media will serve as a crucial channel for communication and dissemination strategies, helping ESNA reach a wider audience. Civil society, as the final beneficiary of enhanced startup ecosystems across Europe, will experience the lasting impacts of ESNA's activities.

In aligning data collection with the diverse needs of these stakeholder groups, the design and specification of the Data Platform will play a pivotal role. The specificity of data fields for startups will cater to the requirements of member organisations, aiding them in policy implementation and decision-making. The platform's scalability will ensure that it can effectively handle the diverse data requirements of startups, investors, researchers, and other stakeholders.

Engagement strategies will be tailored to resonate with the different target groups. Transparent communication will emphasize the value of data contribution to member organisations, while incentive programs will recognize the efforts of startups, investors, and other contributors. The user-friendly interface will cater to the varied needs of different stakeholders, ensuring a seamless experience for all users.

Through collaborative workshops and events, ESNA will actively involve member states, startups, investors, researchers, and other stakeholders, fostering a sense of community and encouraging knowledge exchange. The data gathered through these interactions will not only empower member organisations but will also contribute to the broader impact on national startup ecosystems, ultimately benefiting Europe and its citizens. The strategic deployment of mainstream events and communication channels, including platforms like the Web Summit, will further amplify the reach of ESNA's initiatives, creating a lasting and positive impact on startup ecosystems throughout Europe.

3. EU Startup Definitions and Taxonomy

Regarding the EU Startup definition and Taxonomy, the ongoing activities are split in three action areas:

- Desk research on country level regulations and key entities across the startup ecosystem.
- Questionnaires and Surveys to gather feedback directly from the market, both online and onsite at relevant events like Web Summit in Lisbon.
- Focus groups and workshops to discuss with market leaders and experts to better understand the definitions of a Startup, scaleup and other key terms.

All these action areas are always defined with an emphasis on open collaboration with other European entities and initiatives, such as EISMEA project to develop an European Startup Scoreboard and corresponding definitions

Desk Research

Desk research on the EU Startup taxonomy topic is conducted on two different fronts. One front focuses on researching current laws and regulations across EU and non-EU countries regarding startups. Different countries have different laws and definitions they apply locally to classify and define Startups.

The second front focuses on researching relevant entities within the startup ecosystem to understand ongoing discussions, conclusions and potential frameworks and definitions for startups. Entities such as OECD, G20 Startup Group, European Scaleup Institute, EC taskforces and initiatives that have their own conclusions on potential definitions.

Questionnaires and Surveys

ESNA developed an EU Startup definition survey that was conducted onsite during the Innovation Radar Summit 2023 and Web Summit 2023, collecting over 316 responses. There are plans to make the survey available online and at other relevant events. The survey consists of 10 specific questions designed to identify the relevant indicators that define a startup and a scaleup, along with additional demographic questions about the respondents.

ESNA Europe Startup Nations Alliance

Welcome to ESNA's "Startup" survey!
10 quick questions on startup definition

Start press Enter ↵

1 -> What characterizes a startup? *

Choose as many as you like

A Innovation

B Scalability

C Growth

D Revenue

E Other

OK

Focus groups

The objective is to define focus groups and workshops to discuss the EU Startup taxonomy topic. Events like the ESNA Advisory Board meetings are ideal for allocating time for in-depth discussions on the topic and receiving feedback from expert market voices on potential definitions and relevant indicators.

4. Data Collection and Analysis Methodology

Desk Research

Our helpdesk research process includes a comprehensive analysis of the data collected and a proposal for the definition of a "startup" in the context of ESNA's Signatory Countries.

At this stage, we carefully review the data collected from various sources, with a particular focus on government and regulatory websites. We use a structured methodology that includes data cleaning, data organisation, data analysis and interpretation.

Data cleaning

We ensure the accuracy and consistency of our dataset by systematically eliminating duplicate entries, correcting errors and standardising data formats. This critical step lays the foundation for reliable and trustworthy analysis.

Data organisation

Our approach involves categorising and structuring the data using appropriate tools such as spreadsheets or databases. This organisation is critical for clarity and ease of reference, ensuring that all relevant information is readily accessible.

Data analysis

We use a range of data analysis techniques, including Power BI visualizations. These methods allow us to extract valuable insights, identify key trends and reveal significant patterns within the dataset.

Interpretation

This step involves interpreting the results of our data analysis in the context of our research objectives. This interpretation helps us to identify trends, outliers and correlations that contribute to a deeper understanding of the characteristics and challenges associated with startups.

As part of this process, we aim to propose EU Startup Taxonomy. This proposal is based on the findings of our data analysis and aims to facilitate a clear and consistent understanding of startups in the Signatory countries. Our goal is to provide all stakeholders with well-founded insights that are easy to understand, enabling them to make informed decisions and address startup-related issues effectively.

5. Challenges and Risk Mitigation

Data Gathering for ESNA Data Platform

The following are challenges related to data gathering for the ESNA Data Platform

- Data source reliability: it is important to ensure that the data sources used for the Data Platform are reliable and provide consistent data.
- Data format consistency among sources is also crucial to consider when exploring the best ways to integrate and aggregate the data. The same information may be provided in different formats, making data aggregation more challenging.
- Data integration: some sources provide nearly real-time setups via properly documented APIs while others primarily offer data exports in Excel or CSV format.
- Customer centricity: understanding the expectations and potential key performance indicators (KPIs), dashboards, and use cases that users of the Data Platform would like is essential. This understanding allows for the proper mapping of user needs with the right data sources and values.

- Public Procurement approach: to better acquire the necessary licenses, it is important to consider a public procurement approach. Some data sources, such as Eurostat or OCDE provide access to their data for free, while others, like Dealroom or Pitchbook, require a license fee to be paid. Any purchase should adhere to public procurement procedures and timelines.

To mitigate some of the risks, we are considering the following:

- Allocate sufficient time of high quality to the scoping phase of the Data Platform to understand its complexity, potential implementation scenarios, and to manage expectations with stakeholders. Multiple interviews will be conducted with stakeholders to gather customer centric requirements.
- Optimize the implementation process by pivoting to inhouse expertise for certain technical developments and data platform integrations.
- Leverage existing solutions and technologies as much as possible to ensure a smooth implementation.

EU Startup Taxonomy

The main challenge lies in the current level of fragmentation regarding definitions. Different entities hold varying perspectives, making it difficult to achieve harmonization. Additionally, on a policy level, countries introduce their own Startup Laws with differing interpretations and definitions based on their respective realities. Harmonizing data from these diverse fronts will be crucial for the successful development of an EU Startup Taxonomy.

To comprehensively address this challenge, ESNA collaborates with multiple EU entities and organisations such as EISMEA, DG RTD, DG GROW, Dealflow/IR Bridge; leveraging ESNA's network of Focal Points and ESNA's Advisory Board to gather all relevant information for the final EU Startup Taxonomy.

6. Conclusion and Recommendations

- The list of potential data sources for our Data Platform is still being refined, with clear objectives to combine sources comprising both startup-related data and macroeconomic data.
- The development of the EU Startup taxonomy is still ongoing. ESNA is leveraging other project initiatives on similar topics to harmonize the EU taxonomy and define comparable indicators. The primary challenge lies in reaching consensus.
- The current deliverable represents an interim step that will align with the implementation and usage of the Data Platform. Aggregation and filtering capabilities will be defined based on the EU Startup Taxonomy
- Several Data sources have already been explored such as Dealroom, Crunchbase, Eurostat and OECD, with initial integration tests successfully conducted via PowerBI. Concurrently, the scoping exercise for the Data Platform is underway and to be concluded by September 2024. The convergence of these efforts will culminate in the

MVP of the ESNA Data Platform by Q1CY2025, with subsequent feature releases planned after the launch.

7. Appendices

EU Startup definitions – ongoing desk research

The following activities are part of the desk research work that ESNA has conducted over the past few months:

- ESNA conducted an initial analysis on current regulations in each EU country related to startups. Some countries, such as Portugal, Spain and Estonia have specific Startup Laws with defined terms, while others do not yet have specific laws in this regard. The following image shows an example of the internal summary per country presented as part of the research:

- Among all EU countries analysed, we examined relevant quantitative values. The following are the Minimum Common values among countries, meaning a Startup company would fit the definition in any country:

Criteria	Common Values
Age	<10 years
Revenue	<50M€
B/S	<43M€
Employees	<250

- After conducting research across multiple entities and organisations, such as DG GROW, OECD, G20 and ESI, we concluded that the definition of a startup can be split into three dimensions, with varying values depending on the definition applied:
 - Quantitative values, such as age, revenue and number of employees
 - Qualitative values, such as innovation, growth and scalability
 - Country/Region regulations, such as the percentage of employees from a given country and the location of a company's headquarters.

- It is also relevant to consider a potential split between academia and investment dimensions as part of the analysis. Values such as “VC-backed company”, spin-off company are also important to consider in the discussion of the startup taxonomy.
- The following framework is worth exploring to define the EU Startup Taxonomy. This framework can be used not only to define startups but also other categories such as scaleups, deep tech, etc.

EU Startup taxonomy survey

Full set of survey questions for EU startup definition

<p>1. In your opinion, what of the following words characterize a startup? (MCMA)</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> Innovation Scalability Growth Revenue Other (please specify)
<p>2. What do you consider the typical “Age range” of a Startup to be? (MCSA)</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> Less than 1 year Up to 5 years Up to 10 years More than 10 years Not relevant
<p>3. What do you consider the “Yearly Revenue range” of a Startup to be? (MCSA)</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> Less than 100K EUR Up to 1M EUR Up to 50M EUR More than 50M EUR Not relevant
<p>4. What do you consider the “Employee range” of a Startup to be? (MCSA)</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> Up to 10 employees

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> b. Up to 50 employees c. Up to 250 employees d. Up to 500 employees e. More than 500 employees f. Not relevant
5. What role does “innovation” play in the definition of a startup, from 0 to 10
6. What role does “scalability” play in the definition of a startup, from 0 to 10
7. What role does “digital-based” play in the definition of a startup, from 0 to 10
8. What role does “deeptech” play in the definition of a startup, from 0 to 10
<p>9. In your opinion, what distinguishes a Startup from a Scaleup? (MCMA)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. Growth b. Scalability c. Company Size d. Profitability e. Product-Market fit f. Market Cap g. Other (please specify)
<p>10. In your opinion, at what YoY Revenue Growth does a Startup transition to a Scaleup? (MCSA)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. 10% YoY Revenue Growth b. 20% YoY Revenue Growth c. 30% YoY Revenue Growth d. Other (Please specify)
11. What is your nationality? (MCSA)
<p>12. Years of experience in the Startup Ecosystem?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. Less than 1 year b. 1-3 years c. 3-5 years d. More than 5 years
<p>13. What’s your profession?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. Founder b. Startup employee c. Policymaker / Government d. Corporate e. Self-employed f. Investor g. Student h. Incubator i. Researcher/Academia j. Consultant k. Job seeker
14. What industry do you work for?

EU Startup definition and taxonomy survey - Websummit 2023 dashboard Results

